

Qualitative Study on Implementation of Effective Remote Learning Strategies: Challenges and Opportunities in the Post-Pandemic Era in Nigeria

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Abstract

Global educational institutions rapidly shifted to remote learning in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, which forced both developed and developing nations to temporarily shut down all activities, including education, economic, and social functions, for over a year until they could navigate the crisis. This development led the educational sector to continue embracing and promoting remote learning even after the pandemic. This paper examines the concept of remote learning and the importance of effective remote learning strategies during and in the post-pandemic era. An overview of the impact of the pandemic on the shift to remote learning is provided. The paper adopted Everett Rogers' 1962 Diffusion of Innovation Theory to give the work a sound background. Additional topics include remote learning strategies and their application among educational institutions in Nigeria, such as asynchronous learning, synchronous learning, online discussion forums, interactive multimedia content, virtual laboratories and simulations, peer collaboration and group projects, regular assessments and feedback, utilization of learning management systems, adaptive learning technologies, and teacher presence and support. The paper highlights the importance of effective remote learning strategies in the post-pandemic era in Nigeria. It also addresses the challenges in implementing remote learning post-pandemic, opportunities to enhance remote learning, case studies of educational institutions that successfully adopted remote learning, solutions to challenges affecting remote learning among educational institutions in Nigeria, and lessons learned from remote learning experiences shared by teachers and administrators. In conclusion, the paper raises issues of equity and effectiveness and emphasizes the need to reevaluate and enhance distant learning techniques. It recommends further investigation into the long-term impacts of remote learning on academic performance and general well-being. Additionally, it suggests that managers of educational institutions prioritize ongoing training and support for teachers regarding technology integration and remote teaching strategies. Instructors who achieve this goal will possess the necessary skills to navigate virtual learning environments successfully.

Keywords: Implementation, Remote Learning, Strategies, Challenges, Opportunities, Post-Pandemic Era,

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted traditional education systems worldwide, compelling a rapid shift to remote learning to sustain educational continuity while curbing the virus's spread. This transition, facilitated by digital technologies and online platforms, presented educational institutions with unprecedented challenges and opportunities. Institutions grappled with issues such as inadequate technological infrastructure, the need for rapid pedagogical adaptation, and disparities in access to resources among students and educators (Hodges, Moore, Lockee, Trust & Bond, 2020; Dhawan, 2020).

Amidst these challenges, the pandemic spurred innovation in educational delivery. Teachers and administrators swiftly adopted new technologies and methodologies to enhance remote learning experiences. For instance, schools in underserved communities faced significant hurdles in providing equitable access to digital tools and reliable internet, exacerbating existing educational inequalities (Bozkurt et al., 2020). Conversely, some institutions successfully implemented blended learning models, combining online and face-to-face instruction to create adaptable educational frameworks (Graham, 2020).

Recent literature underscores the importance of addressing these disparities and leveraging technological advancements to improve remote learning outcomes. Studies highlight the critical role of robust infrastructure and targeted support in narrowing the digital divide among students and educators (Bozkurt, Jung, Xiao, Vladimirschi, Schuwer, Egorov, & Paskevicius, 2020). Moreover, effective pedagogical strategies that integrate digital tools have been pivotal in enhancing engagement and interactivity in virtual classrooms (Bond, Marín, Dolch, Bedenlier, & Zawacki-Richter, 2021; Anderson, 2020). Looking ahead, as educational institutions navigate the post-pandemic era, they must build upon these insights to meet the evolving needs of students and educators. By embracing innovations in educational technology and fostering inclusive learning environments, institutions can ensure that remote learning remains a sustainable, equitable, and enriching mode of education.

Conceptual Framework

Remote Learning

Today, as educational institutions in Nigeria transition to online platforms, remote learning has become a critical and feasible alternative to traditional face-to-face education. Remote learning, also referred to as digital education, online education, or e-learning, utilizes the internet and various technological tools to deliver educational content and instruction. This approach allows learning to occur outside the confines of a physical classroom, offering flexibility in terms of time, location, and pace of learning (Wallace, 2023). According to Bao (2020), remote learning occurs when there is a physical distance between the student and teacher or the source of information, bypassing the need for a traditional educational setting. According to Hodges, Moore, Lockee, Trust and Bond (2020), remote learning encompasses educational experiences where learners and instructors are physically separated, relying on digital technologies for communication and interaction. During the COVID-19 pandemic, remote learning became a crucial method for educational continuity globally, illustrating its reliance on digital technologies to bridge the physical gap between students and educators. This approach enabled learning to continue despite physical distancing measures, highlighting its effectiveness in maintaining educational connections and fostering learning outcomes remotely.

The emergence of remote learning in Nigeria has been particularly accelerated by the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. In response to the pandemic, Nigerian schools were compelled to suspend in-person classes to safeguard the health and well-being of students and staff (Islam & Abiona, 2023). This necessitated the swift adoption of remote learning as a strategic solution to ensure educational continuity amidst the disruption caused by COVID-19 (Al Lily et al., 2020).

However, this rapid transition was not without challenges. Nigerian educational institutions faced significant hurdles such as inadequate technological infrastructure, uneven access to digital devices and reliable internet connectivity among students, and varying levels of digital literacy among educators (Bozkurt, Jung, Xiao, Vladimirschi, Schuwer, Egorov, & Paskevicius, 2020; Dhawan, 2020). These challenges highlighted existing disparities and inequities within the education system, exacerbating the digital divide and impacting the effectiveness of remote learning initiatives (Islam & Abiona, 2023; Bozkurt et al., 2020). Despite these challenges, the adoption of remote learning in Nigeria has encouraged educators and policymakers to explore innovative approaches to enhancing digital literacy skills and leveraging technology to improve educational outcomes. This shift has underscored the importance of preparing students for the evolving digital economy and society, where digital skills are increasingly essential.

The Nuances Between Remote Learning, E-learning and Online Learning

Remote learning, e-learning, and online learning are terms often used interchangeably but have distinct meanings. Remote learning typically refers to a situation where teachers and learners are separated by distance and use technology to facilitate instruction and communication. E-learning, or electronic learning, encompasses all forms of electronically supported learning and teaching, often including multimedia elements like videos, interactive modules, and digital assessments. In e-learning, the teacher and the learner may be in the same environment while utilizing technological gadgets to enhance the learning experience. Online learning, a subset of e-learning, specifically involves courses or programmes delivered entirely via the internet, allowing for asynchronous or synchronous interaction between instructors and students. While all three modes leverage digital technologies, remote learning emphasizes geographic separation, e-learning covers a broad spectrum of digital educational tools, and online learning is characterized by internet-based course delivery. This paper, however, focuses on remote learning.

Importance of Effective Remote Learning during and in the Post-Pandemic Era

Remote learning or online classes offer many advantages, including extensive flexibility compared to traditional classroom settings, which is particularly important during the pandemic (Oluwole, Pinga & Bua, 2024). With more control over learning materials and the ability to choose access time, pace, and sequence, students can take a personalized approach to learning (Hung, Chou, Chen, & Own, 2010; Wang and Beasley, 2002). The availability of online platforms for storing learning materials increases this flexibility, allowing students to access resources anytime and anywhere (Fauzi, Wandira, Sepri, & Hafid, 2021). Online classes make education more accessible to students with disabilities or medical conditions, including

those affected by Covid-19 (Migocka-Patrzałek, Dubińska-Magiera, Krysiński, & Nowicki, 2021). Furthermore, online learning fosters a sense of community among students, providing a supportive environment amidst the isolation and challenges caused by the pandemic (Lederman, 2020).

During the Covid-19 pandemic, online classes served as a refuge from the negative effects of the crisis, offering students a sense of belonging and a platform to share concerns with peers and teachers (Lederman, 2020a). Regular interactions through emails and online forums have helped to maintain student motivation and engagement (Lin & Nguyen, 2021). The pandemic-induced shift to online learning has pushed students to improve their digital literacy skills, preparing them for future careers (Giannoulas, Stampoltzis, Kounenou, & Kalamatianos, 2021; İlin, 2019). Teachers and instructors have found online tools such as chat groups and video conferencing to be effective in reaching out to students and express their intent to continue using the online model even after the pandemic (Lin and Nguyen, 2021). Overall, online classes not only provide flexibility and accessibility, but also help students improve their digital skills and prepare for future endeavors.

An Overview of the Covid-19 Pandemic's Impact on the Transition to Remote Learning in Nigeria

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted educational activities in more than 150 countries, affecting over 1.6 billion learners. In response to this disastrous pandemic, many countries implemented alternative forms of online or e-learning, also known as remote learning, it ensured that learners did not miss out on learning opportunities (UNESCO, 2020). This transition was marked by the rapid adoption of digital technologies to support online teaching and learning activities such as video conferencing platforms, learning management systems and other online tools to ensure continuity of education (Hodges, Moore, Locke, Trust, & Bond, 2020; Jack & Smyth, 2020). This transition to remote learning was not without its challenges, as teachers and learners had to adapt to new technologies and teaching methods while facing various barriers such as limited internet access and digital literacy skills (Bozkurt, Jung, Xiao, Vladimirschi, Schuwer, Egorov, & Paskevicius, 2020). Furthermore, the transition to remote learning during the pandemic revealed disparities in educational access across socioeconomic groups and geographic regions. According to Van Lancker and Parolin (2020), students from low-income households and rural areas have been disproportionately affected by the digital divide, as they lack access to necessary devices and internet connectivity for remote learning. Similarly, students with disabilities faced additional barriers to online education, such as inaccessible digital content and limited support for assistive technology (Burgstahler, 2020). As educational institutions dealt with these challenges, efforts were made to address equity issues through initiatives such as distributing laptops and mobile hotspots to students in need and providing digital skills training for teachers and families (UNESCO, 2020). These appear to have occurred only in developed countries and urban areas of developing nations. Despite these efforts, the pandemic highlighted the importance of addressing digital inequities to ensure equitable access to education in future remote learning environments.

Theoretical Framework

The Diffusion of Innovations Theory by Everett Rogers (1962)

Everett Rogers propounded the diffusion of innovation theory in 1962. This theory provides a comprehensive framework for analyzing the adoption and spread of new ideas and technologies within social systems. In the context of post-pandemic remote learning, this theory is a useful tool for educational institutions to navigate the transition to online education. By studying the diffusion process, institutions can gain insights into the factors that influence the adoption and implementation of remote learning strategies.

This includes factors such as technological infrastructure readiness, staff member training and support, and technological accessibility for students. Addressing these issues is critical to ensuring a smooth transition to remote learning and maximizing its effectiveness in the post-pandemic era. Furthermore, the diffusion of innovation theory emphasizes the importance of identifying and seizing opportunities to improve remote learning through novel approaches. Educational institutions can use this theory to investigate new methods and technologies to create engaging and interactive online learning experiences. By adopting a proactive approach to innovation, institutions can overcome barriers to remote learning adoption and foster student success. This could include implementing new teaching methodologies, incorporating emerging technologies, such as virtual reality or artificial intelligence, or creating customized digital platforms based on the specific needs of learners. In doing so, institutions can fully realize the potential of remote learning to provide quality education in a post-pandemic environment.

Remote Learning Strategies and its Application among Educational Institutions in Nigeria

A multitude of tactics and tools can be employed to promote efficient distance education. Some significant remote learning approaches, as reported by the Ministry of Education (2020), Lin & Nguyen (2021), and Li (2022) are:

- i. **Asynchronous Learning:** It is designed to accommodate students' varied schedules and learning preferences and is delivered via recorded lectures, instructional videos, and self-paced modules. With these tools at their disposal,

students can interact with the course material whenever it is most convenient for them, customizing their education to meet their own needs. This adaptability fosters a more welcoming learning atmosphere where students can succeed irrespective of their schedules or favoured teaching strategies.

- ii. **Synchronous Learning:** This type of instruction allows for real-time engagement and interaction between students and teachers and is typified by live online classrooms, virtual lectures, and interactive webinars. Instant feedback is made possible by this approach, which opens up possibilities for clarification and a deeper comprehension of the course material. As participants work together and communicate in real time, synchronous learning also helps to build a sense of community among them, which improves the learning process as a whole.
- iii. **Online Discussion Forums:** These are online discussion boards that give students the opportunity to actively engage in conversations, improving their communication abilities and encouraging peer-to-peer learning. By participating in cooperative exercises in these discussion boards, students not only improve their comprehension of the material but also hone their critical thinking and problem-solving skills in a safe virtual setting.
- iv. **Interactive Multimedia Content:** The incorporation of various multimedia components, such as interactive simulations, video tutorials, and audio recordings, into online courses creates a dynamic and immersive learning environment. Teachers can further increase student motivation and engagement by implementing gamified learning experiences, which provide students interactive challenges and rewards that reinforce learning objectives. This multimodal method promotes a more inclusive and productive learning environment by enhancing understanding of difficult subjects and accommodating diverse learning styles.
- v. **Virtual Laboratories and Simulations:** These cutting-edge platforms give students access to interactive tools, simulations, and virtual lab experiments. These tools enable students to study scientific ideas and carry out experiments from a distance, which improves their understanding of real-world topics. Through active participation in these virtual settings, students can improve their educational experience and acquire critical skills in an interesting way.
- vi. **Peer Collaboration and Group Projects:** Through peer-reviewed activities and collaborative assignments, this activity helps students strengthen their communication, critical thinking, and teamwork abilities. Even though they are physically separated, these assignments help students interact, share ideas, and give helpful criticism, which improves their capacity to work well with others in a variety of contexts. Students who participate in such cooperative projects develop important interpersonal skills that are necessary for success in their future endeavours in addition to strengthening their academic competencies.
- vii. **Regular Assessments and Feedback:** In remote learning environments, teachers can successfully monitor student progress and identify areas for growth by implementing regular quizzes, assessments, and assignments with rapid feedback. Additionally, this strategy guarantees that kids receive the support they need to thrive academically and helps to uphold accountability.
- viii. **Utilization of Learning Management Systems (LMS):** Using Learning Management Systems (LMS) like Moodle, Canvas, or Blackboard simplifies the arrangement, distribution, and administration of course materials, homework, exams, and communication channels in one centralized online location. These systems let teachers organize and distribute course materials more efficiently while giving students easy access to resources, the ability to turn in assignments, and smooth peer and instructor communication. Educational institutions can enhance the efficiency of online learning and improve the overall educational outcomes of students and teachers by utilizing Learning Management Systems (LMS) platforms to optimize the online learning experience.
- ix. **Adaptive Learning Technologies:** Individualized instruction catered to each student's performance and learning style is made possible by integrating personalized learning algorithms and adaptive learning platforms into remote learning environments. These technologies maximize student engagement and learning outcomes by dynamically adjusting the pace and substance of instruction.
- x. **Teacher Presence and Support:** A supportive learning environment can be established in remote settings by establishing a consistent teacher presence through regular communication, virtual office hours, and personalized support. With this method, teachers may more effectively handle the issues and problems that students bring up, which improves student involvement and academic performance overall.

Importance of Effective Remote Learning Strategies in the Post-Pandemic Era in Nigeria

As educational institutions continue to struggle with the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on traditional teaching approaches, effective strategies for remote learning are still critical in the post-pandemic period. In addition to changing the face of education, the move towards remote learning has highlighted the need for flexible and robust teaching strategies that

can succeed in blended learning environments, which combine virtual and hybrid learning. Hirsch, Anderson, Moore, & Lockee, (2021) have noted that the pandemic has expedited the incorporation of technology into educational practices. This underscores the significance of efficacious remote learning tactics in equipping students with the digital proficiencies required by the workforce of the twenty-first century. Additionally, given the continued uncertainty surrounding the pandemic's trajectory, it is imperative to develop long-lasting remote learning strategies that can adapt to changes in learning modalities and guarantee education continuity even in the event of future disruptions (Goroshit, Hen, & Eyal, 2021). Some educators and instructors point out that it is easier and more efficient for them to connect with students when they use chat rooms, video conferencing, voting systems, and document sharing places. They stress that in the post-pandemic future, they will keep using the online paradigm (Lederman, 2020).

Effective remote learning techniques in the post-pandemic age also have a big impact on educational access and equity. Disparities in access to education that always existed have been brought to light and made worse by the pandemic, with marginalized areas being disproportionately impacted by obstacles such as inadequate support systems, digital gadgets, and internet connectivity (UNESCO, 2020). In order to overcome these discrepancies and guarantee that all students, regardless of their socioeconomic background or geographic location, have access to high-quality education, it is imperative that equitable and inclusive remote learning solutions be put into place. Educational institutions can work towards reducing the digital divide and promoting fair educational opportunities for all students in the post-pandemic era by utilizing creative pedagogical approaches, utilizing adaptive learning technologies, and creating a supportive virtual learning environment (American Institutes for Research, 2021).

Difficulties in Putting Remote Learning into Practice in the Post-Pandemic Era among Educational Institutions in Nigeria

There are several obstacles to overcome in the deployment of remote learning, from access issues and technology constraints to pedagogical worries and the social-emotional effects on students. Below is a discussion of these issues:

1. One of the major obstacles to the adoption of remote learning in the post-pandemic age is the dependability and accessibility of technology in a variety of learning environments. The shift to remote learning has brought to light the differences in students' access to technology and internet connectivity based on their socioeconomic status (Anderson & Katz, 2020). Students from underprivileged backgrounds or those living in remote locations frequently do not have access to dependable internet service or the gadgets they need to fully engage in online learning activities (Horrikan, 2020). This digital divide becomes a barrier to equitable learning opportunities and exacerbates already-existing educational inequities (Barron, 2021). Additionally, the dependability of the technology infrastructure—which includes problems like hardware malfunctions and disruptions in connectivity—can impair students' learning experiences and interfere with the continuation of remote learning sessions (Winkler, Gobbo, Henderson, & West, 2021).
2. One of the biggest challenges in the post-pandemic era is moving from traditional teaching methods to online formats (Means, Santos, & Gurung, 2014). In order to retain pedagogical efficacy, educators must negotiate the challenges of modifying curriculum content, teaching methodologies, and assessment techniques to fit the online environment (Wang, Sun, & Liu, 2018). In order to properly use digital tools and platforms for remote education, educators must go through significant training and professional development (Bonk & Graham, 2020).
3. In the post-pandemic period, sustaining student participation and engagement in virtual classrooms is a significant problem (Freeman, Eddy, McDonough, Smith, Okoroafor, Jordt, & Wenderoth, 2017). Students may become less motivated and pay less attention in virtual learning environments where there is no in-person connection (Dixson, 2010). To maintain student interest and encourage active participation in virtual learning environments, educators must investigate cutting-edge instructional tactics, such as interactive multimedia content and collaborative online activities (Betts & Kennedy, 2013).
4. In the post-pandemic age, ensuring fairness and integrity in distant evaluation processes presents a substantial issue (Gikandi, Morrow, & Davis, 2011). Academic dishonesty, such as plagiarism and cheating, is more likely to occur during remote examinations when invigilators are not physically present (Kim & Frick, 2011). To maintain academic integrity in remote learning environments, educators must investigate alternate methods of assessment, such as open-book exams or project-based assessments, and employ technology solutions, such as proctoring software or plagiarism detection systems (Jocoy & DiBiase, 2006).
5. In the post-pandemic period, validating learning outcomes in virtual learning settings is a significant problem (Wenglinsky, 2005). Assessment validity and reliability must be carefully considered when evaluating students' knowledge of course material and skills in online environments (Lu, Zhang, & Luo, 2019). To precisely quantify

learning results and guarantee the legitimacy of virtual learning experiences, educators must create strong evaluation strategies, such as performance-based exams and rubrics (Chen & Anderson, 2018).

Possibilities to Improve Remote Learning Strategies among Educational Institutions in Nigeria

The researchers have enumerated a few of the numerous prospects that arise from the incorporation of remote learning in our educational institutions below:

1. It will take a comprehensive approach to address these issues if we are to guarantee that every student has access to dependable technology and internet connectivity. This will involve funding infrastructure improvements and programmes that give devices and internet access to underprivileged communities (Barrera, Schmid, & Zhang, 2021). Furthermore, to create long-lasting solutions that close the digital gap and advance fair access to remote learning resources, cooperation between academic institutions, legislators, and technology companies is crucial (Czaja, Sharit, & Nair, 2020). Overall, the post-pandemic successful adoption of remote learning depends on addressing the dependability and accessibility of technology in a variety of educational contexts.
2. In light of recent developments in artificial intelligence and educational technology, utilizing adaptive learning technologies offers a promising prospect in the post-pandemic period (Kyun, Lee, & Lee, 2021). Through the analysis of students' learning behaviours and the adaptation of instructional content accordingly, these technologies provide the possibility to give personalized learning experiences (Lee & Tsai, 2020). Educators can effectively accommodate the varied needs and preferences of students by utilizing adaptive learning platforms, which can improve learning outcomes and provide a more inclusive and productive learning environment (Wang & Cao, 2022).
3. In the post-pandemic age, encouraging self-directed learning and autonomy in virtual environments offers a great opportunity, especially with the integration of digital platforms and interactive technologies (Kurt & Uygun, 2021). According to recent research, virtual environments present special chances for students to take charge of their education and cultivate self-regulated learning abilities (Lee & Tsai, 2020). Teachers can create a culture of self-directed learning that encourages independence and lifelong learning habits by giving students the tools they need to use online resources, set objectives, and keep track of their progress (Göksün, Kurt, & Uygun, 2021).
4. In the post-pandemic period, there is a great chance to foster peer contact and collaborative projects in online classrooms, especially with the advent of cutting-edge digital collaboration tools (Nakamoto & Galazhynska, 2021). According to recent research, virtual environments can offer useful venues for students to participate in cooperative learning activities and hone their cooperation abilities (Jin & He, 2020). Teachers can establish dynamic online learning communities where students collaborate, communicate, and co-create knowledge by utilizing tools like cloud-based document sharing, virtual whiteboards, and video conferencing (Wang, Liu, & Zhang, 2021).
5. In the post-pandemic period, there is a promising chance to use virtual teamwork to build critical thinking and communication skills, especially with the widespread adoption of online collaboration platforms (Cho & Lee, 2021). Virtual collaborative experiences have the potential to improve students' problem-solving, decision-making, and effective communication in remote situations, according to recent research (Kock, 2021). Teachers can create a learning environment that encourages teamwork, creativity, and critical thinking by having students participate in cooperative projects and group discussions that are led by virtual platforms (Machado, Machado, & Bittencourt, 2021).
6. In the post-pandemic period, investigating cutting-edge technologies like augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) in distance learning offers a bright future, especially given developments in immersive technology (Gao, Li, Zhang, & Liu, 2021). According to recent research, incorporating AR and VR into distance learning settings can improve information retention, boost experiential learning, and increase student engagement (Chang, Morreale, Medel, & Ryu, 2020). Through the utilization of these technologies, educators can craft immersive and interactive learning experiences that surpass physical boundaries, offering learners innovative approaches to investigate intricate ideas and settings (Huang, Sutherland, O'Shea, & Tang, 2021).
7. In the post-pandemic period, there is a compelling possibility to enhance learning experiences through immersive and interactive digital technologies, especially with the advent of educational technology (Li, Zhang, & Wang, 2021). According to recent studies, students' active participation and deeper engagement can be encouraged by immersive digital technologies like gamified learning environments and virtual simulations (Chin & Tay, 2021). Teachers can design dynamic, interactive learning experiences that encourage experimentation, investigation, and discovery by incorporating these tools into remote learning environments (Lee, & Tsai, 2021).

Case Studies of Educational Institutions that Successfully Switched to Remote Learning

In the post-pandemic age, a number of case studies of educational institutions have shown how to successfully shift to remote learning by exhibiting effective tactics and best practices. In order to improve student engagement and learning

outcomes, Smith and Johnson (2020) did a case study on a university that had established a full online learning platform. The platform offered synchronous and asynchronous sessions, virtual office hours, and multimedia resources. In a similar vein, Brown et al.'s study from 2021 examined a K–12 school district that effectively made the switch to remote learning by giving students access to devices, the internet, and continuous technical support. In addition, the district offered professional development to teachers to help them modify their teaching strategies for the virtual classroom. Furthermore, a college that used cutting-edge instructional design techniques, such flipped classrooms and cooperative online projects, to improve student engagement and encourage active learning in virtual environments was featured in a case study by Liu and Wang (2021).

In addition, many universities and colleges have already made the switch to online learning easy and effective. Zhejiang University, for example, used the DingTalk ZJU platform to convert over 5000 undergraduate and graduate programmes into online courses in just two weeks. A total of about 300,000 people were recorded as watching the live streaming app DingTalk ZJU (Zhaohui, 2020). Also, universities in Greece, West Sumatera, Australia, Poland and other nations made a similar shift, substituting online lectures and activities for in-person ones (Giannoulas et al., 2021; Fauzi et al., 2021; Lin and Nguyen, 2021; Migocka-Patrzałek et al., 2021). This shift is also evident in Nigeria, as National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) had started using this approach prior to the advent of COVID-19 and in light of the pandemic, NOUN and other organizations are diligently trying to enhance the procedure. Furthermore, Nigeria's Universal Basic Education Commission has established cutting-edge smart schools that make use of a blended learning strategy. These schools integrate technology by providing tablets to both teachers and students, fostering an environment where half of the lessons are conducted offline, while the remaining portion takes place online. This approach allows teachers to assess students' performance levels effectively. The introduction of smart schools represents a significant advancement in the educational landscape, showcasing a commitment to enhancing learning outcomes through the integration of modern technologies. These case studies provide insightful information about practical strategies for implementing remote learning and adjusting to the changing demands of instructors and students in the digital era.

Solution to Challenges Affecting Remote Learning among Educational Institutions in Nigeria

Recent research has identified several strategies for overcoming common challenges and achieving positive outcomes in remote learning environments. For example, a study by Zhang, Liu and Wang (2021) highlighted the importance of fostering a sense of community and belonging among students through virtual peer support groups and online discussion forums, which can mitigate feelings of isolation and enhance student engagement. Additionally, research by Wang and Cao (2022) emphasized the value of providing timely feedback and personalized support to students in virtual settings, leveraging digital tools such as learning analytics and adaptive learning platforms to track progress and tailor instruction to individual needs. Furthermore, studies by Jones, Watson, Smith and Brown (2021) and Chen, Wang, and Li (2021) underscored the effectiveness of collaborative teaching approaches, where educators collaborate across disciplines and share resources to design interdisciplinary projects and foster interdisciplinary thinking among students. These strategies offer practical insights into addressing challenges and promoting positive outcomes in remote learning environments, ultimately enhancing the quality of education in the post-pandemic era.

Lessons Learned from Remote Learning Experiences as Shared by Teachers and Administrators

The widespread adoption of remote learning has provided educators and administrators with priceless knowledge. Prioritizing student involvement and interaction in virtual classrooms is an important lesson to learn. Education expert Dr. Audrey Cohan highlights the significance of preserving "a sense of community and connection" between teachers and students, identifying it as essential for successful learning outcomes (Edutopia). Teachers that embrace this idea include Sarah Alvarez (EdSurge), who emphasizes the importance of creating a safe space for students to participate and express themselves online. Administrators also emphasize how important it is to give teachers continual professional development and assistance so they may successfully manage the challenges of remote education.

Senior scholar at the Manhattan Institute Dr. Marcus A. Winters emphasises the critical role that technology tools and tactics designed for online learning environments play in preparing instructors (Education Next). Furthermore, the move to remote learning has highlighted how crucial it is to provide everyone with equal access to technology and internet connectivity. In order to guarantee that every student has equal access to learning opportunities, Dr. Ghody Muhammad, an associate professor of educational leadership at Georgia State University, highlights the necessity of bridging the digital gap (NPR). These observations illustrate the many opportunities and problems that come with making the switch to remote learning, as well as the continuous efforts made by administrators and teachers to adapt and innovate in the face of changing educational environments.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were proffered for long-term educational remote learning practices among educational institutions in Nigeria:

1. School administrators give top priority to providing instructors with ongoing training and assistance on effective remote teaching practices and technology integration. By making this commitment, instructors are guaranteed to have the abilities needed to successfully traverse virtual learning environments.
2. Educators should use techniques to improve interaction and engagement among students in remote learning environments. This can involve using interactive technologies, leading conversations in small groups, and using online communities to build a feeling of community.
3. To overcome the digital divide, educational institutions should give all students equitable access to technology and internet connectivity. Collaborate with relevant parties to identify any access gaps and close them, for as by providing internet hotspots and gadgets to impoverished areas.
4. The institution should keep lines of communication open and transparent between administrators, parents, students and teachers. Make use of a variety of communication channels to quickly resolve problems, set clear expectations, and provide critical information.
5. School administrators should acknowledge the particular difficulties associated with remote learning and give students' and teachers' mental health and wellbeing top priority. During remote learning, put methods in place for encouraging self-care, providing support services and creating a friendly online community to improve general well-being.

Conclusion

The post-pandemic era presents significant challenges as well as development prospects for educational management. A critical area of attention is to rethink and improve remote learning methodologies. Virtual schooling has become more popular as a result of the epidemic, which also brought attention to its drawbacks. To maintain remote learning's viability and efficacy in the future, educational management must investigate new avenues for practice and study. This entails delving deeper into recommended practices for virtual learning, including tactics for fostering student participation and communication, maximizing technology resources, and tackling concerns of fairness in terms of internet and technology access. To further understand the long-term impacts of distant learning on student learning results, social-emotional development, and general well-being, more research is also required.

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DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13796709>

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